

Human and Cultural Core of Data-Driven Intelligence: An Empirical Model of Enterprise

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ABSTRACT: *In the big data era, competitive intelligence perception capability (CIPC), an organization's ability to detect, interpret, and anticipate environmental changes through systematic data use, has become a strategic imperative. Despite its importance, research on CIPC's organizational antecedents remains limited. Drawing on organizational adaptation theory, big data insight theory, and the reconstructed competitive intelligence value chain, this study employs a sequential mixed-methods design. Grounded theory analysis of 28 interviews reveals two CIPC dimensions—big data-enabled intelligence process capability and intelligence efficacy, and four key organizational enablers: digital strategic orientation, digital institutional process innovation, empowered employee engagement, and data-driven intelligence culture. A Huawei case study validates the emergent model. Quantitative analysis of 378 survey responses confirms all hypotheses via structural equation modeling. Empowered employee engagement exerts the strongest effect on CIPC, and both perceived environmental uncertainty and perceived information source availability positively moderate these relationships. The study offers a validated theoretical model and actionable managerial insights.*

KEYWORDS: *Big data, competitive intelligence perception capability, organizational management, mixed-methods research, structural equation modeling.*

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INTRODUCTION

The convergence of digital technologies and strategic intelligence has fundamentally reshaped corporate decision-making paradigms. In an environment characterized by volatility, uncertainty, complexity, and ambiguity (VUCA), enterprises must rapidly detect emerging threats and opportunities to sustain competitive advantage [1]. Big data—defined by its volume, velocity, variety, veracity, and value—offers unprecedented opportunities for enterprises to enhance their environmental scanning and foresight capabilities [2]. Yet, the mere availability of data does not guarantee strategic insight. The transformation of raw data into actionable intelligence hinges on an organization's *competitive intelligence perception capability* (CIPC), which encompasses the systematic ability to acquire, process, analyze, and apply multi-source, multi-modal data to support proactive decision-making [3].

While prior research has examined competitive intelligence (CI) from functional, technological, and strategic perspectives [4-6], there remains a critical gap in understanding how *organizational management practices* shape CIPC in the big data context. Existing studies often emphasize technical infrastructure or

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individual competencies, overlooking the organizational mechanisms that enable data-driven intelligence to flourish [7]. Furthermore, most empirical investigations lack a robust theoretical foundation and fail to integrate qualitative depth with quantitative rigor [8]. This study addresses these limitations by adopting a grounded-theory-informed, mixed-methods approach to explore the organizational antecedents of CIPC.

Aligned with the call for context-sensitive organizational research [9], we situate our inquiry within the framework of *organizational adaptive change theory* [10,11], which posits that organizations must reconfigure their structures, processes, and cultures to align with environmental shifts—in this case, the data-rich, fast-paced big data ecosystem. We also integrate *big data insight theory* [12] and the *reconstructed competitive intelligence value chain model* [13] to conceptualize CIPC as both a process and an outcome.

This research makes three key contributions. First, it clarifies the conceptual structure of CIPC in the big data environment, distinguishing between *process capability* (how intelligence is generated) and *efficacy* (what it achieves). Second, it identifies and empirically validates four organizational management factors—digital strategic orientation, digital institutional process innovation, empowered employee engagement, and data-driven intelligence culture—as critical enablers of CIPC. Third, it reveals the contingent roles of perceived environmental uncertainty and perceived information source availability as moderators, thereby refining our understanding of boundary conditions.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK AND HYPOTHESIS DEVELOPMENT

Conceptualizing CIPC in the Big Data Context

Traditional notions of CI emphasized reactive monitoring of competitors and markets [4]. However, the big data environment demands a more proactive, predictive, and prescriptive form of intelligence. [3] defines CIPC as “an enterprise’s ability under big data conditions to acquire, understand, and predict changes in the business environment—including macroeconomic, technological, industrial, customer, supply chain, and competitor dimensions—through continuous monitoring, cross-domain integration of multi-source, multi-modal data, and human-machine collaborative analysis to enable foresighted risk warning, opportunity identification, and rapid response.”

Grounded in the competitive intelligence value chain [13], CIPC comprises two interrelated dimensions:

1. **Big Data–Enabled Intelligence Process Capability:** The operational capacity to execute intelligence workflows—acquisition, processing, analysis, and dissemination—using advanced digital tools.
2. **Intelligence Efficacy:** The strategic outcomes of these processes, including decision support, risk warning, opportunity identification, and environmental responsiveness.

This dual-dimension framework aligns with the “input-process-output” logic of organizational systems [14] and provides a comprehensive lens for evaluating CIPC.

Organizational Antecedents of CIPC

Digital Strategic Orientation (DSO) refers to an enterprise’s strategic commitment to leveraging digital technologies for competitive advantage. It includes digital alertness (anticipating disruptions), digital market orientation (understanding customers and competitors through data), and digital innovation orientation (investing in new digital business models). DSO sets the tone for data-centric decision-making and resource allocation [8]. We propose:

H1: Digital strategic orientation positively influences big data–enabled CIPC.

Digital Institutional Process Innovation (DIPI) involves the redesign of organizational rules, procedures, and workflows to embed digital logic into daily operations. In big data contexts, effective DIPI ensures data quality, process agility, and cross-functional coordination [15]. Standardized, efficient, and scientifically designed digital processes reduce information silos and enhance intelligence throughput. Thus:

H2: Digital institutional process innovation positively influences big data–enabled CIPC.

Empowered Employee Engagement (EEE) reflects the extent to which employees are equipped, authorized, and motivated to participate in intelligence activities. In the big data era, frontline employees serve as critical sensors of market dynamics. Empowerment—through digital literacy training, decision-making authority, and collaborative platforms—amplifies organizational sensing capacity [16]. Hence:

H3: Empowered employee engagement positively influences big data–enabled CIPC.

Data-Driven Intelligence Culture (DDIC) denotes shared organizational beliefs that data should guide intelligence and decision-making. This culture fosters openness, innovation, and inclusiveness in data use, encouraging experimentation with new analytical tools and cross-departmental data sharing [17]. A strong DDIC embeds data literacy into organizational DNA. Therefore:

H4: Data-driven intelligence culture positively influences big data–enabled CIPC.

The Mediating Role of CIPC

CIPC serves as a strategic conduit through which organizational capabilities translate into performance. By enabling accurate environmental diagnosis and predictive foresight, CIPC enhances strategic alignment and operational efficiency [13]. Consequently, we posit:

H5: Big data–enabled CIPC positively influences organizational performance.

Furthermore, CIPC mediates the relationships between each organizational antecedent and performance:

H5a–d: CIPC mediates the effects of (a) DSO, (b) DIPI, (c) EEE, and (d) DDIC on organizational performance.

Moderating Effects

Perceived Environmental Uncertainty (PEU)—the degree to which firms perceive their external environment as unpredictable—may intensify the need for robust intelligence capabilities. Under high uncertainty, organizations are more likely to invest in digital orientation, process innovation, and employee empowerment to reduce ambiguity [18]. Thus:

H6a–d: PEU positively moderates the relationships between each organizational antecedent and CIPC.

Perceived Information Source Availability (PISA)—the ease of accessing relevant data—also conditions these relationships. When information is readily available, organizational efforts to build CIPC are more likely to yield returns [19]. Hence:

H7a–d: PISA positively moderates the relationships between each organizational antecedent and CIPC.

RESEARCH DESIGN AND METHODOLOGY

This study employs a sequential exploratory mixed-methods design [20]: qualitative inquiry precedes and informs quantitative validation.

Qualitative Phase: Grounded Theory and Case Study

Semi-structured interviews were conducted with 28 professionals from 10 enterprises across manufacturing, telecommunications, retail, and other sectors. Participants included marketing managers, technical staff, CI specialists, and senior executives. Interview transcripts (68,000+ words) underwent three-stage coding using the procedural grounded theory approach [21]:

- **Open coding** generated 29 initial concepts, clustered into 9 categories.
- **Axial coding** integrated these into two main categories for CIPC: *process capability* and *efficacy*.
- **Selective coding** identified four organizational antecedents.

Theoretical saturation was achieved, confirming conceptual stability (Table 1).

TABLE 1. Open Coding Results for CIPC Dimensions (Excerpt)

Interview Excerpt	Initial Concept	Category
"The company must first obtain high-quality raw data to further analyze and make decisions."	Advanced acquisition technology, high-quality raw data	Intelligence Acquisition Capability
"We use IoT technologies to track multi-modal data in real time..."	Real-time acquisition, multi-modal data, weak signal detection	Intelligence Acquisition Capability
"Many fragmented data are distorted or repetitive... filtering is essential."	Fusion of fragmented multi-modal data	Intelligence Processing Capability
"We provide intelligent push and visualization for decision-makers."	Personalized subscription, intelligent push, visualization	Intelligence Delivery & Application Capability

A case study of Huawei was conducted using secondary data from corporate reports, executive speeches, and academic publications (Table 2). Huawei's practices in digital strategy, process innovation, talent empowerment, and data culture closely aligned with the emergent model.

TABLE 2. Huawei's Practices Aligning with CIPC Antecedents

Organizational Factor	Huawei Practice
Digital Strategic Orientation	"Limitless Survival" scenario simulation; dynamic competitor/customer databases
Digital Institutional Process Innovation	Mandatory digital reporting of frontline sales intelligence
Empowered Employee Engagement	"Let those who hear the gunfire call for artillery" frontline empowerment model
Data-Driven Intelligence Culture	Internal "Xinsheng Community" for open intelligence sharing and discussion

Quantitative Phase: Survey and Analysis

Based on qualitative insights and literature review, an initial scale was developed. After pretesting (n = 159), a final questionnaire was administered to 626 enterprises, yielding 378 valid responses (73.26% effective rate). The sample was predominantly from manufacturing (69.04%) and included state-owned (29.66%) and private firms (41.79%) (Table 3).

TABLE 3. Descriptive Statistics of Survey Sample (n = 378)

Characteristic	Category	Frequency	Percentage
Industry	Manufacturing	261	69.04%
	Services	19	5.02%
	Retail/Wholesale	42	11.11%
	Telecommunications	31	8.20%
	Other	25	6.63%
Firm Ownership	State-Owned	112	29.66%
	Private	158	41.79%
	Foreign-Owned	56	14.81%
	Other	52	13.74%

Measurement models were validated through confirmatory factor analysis (CFA). All constructs showed good fit (Table 4). Common method bias was assessed via Harman's single-factor test, with the first factor explaining only 33.98% of variance.

TABLE 4. Confirmatory Factor Analysis Results for Key Constructs

Construct	χ^2/df	RMSEA	CFI	Cronbach's α
CIPC	2.365	0.060	0.968	0.849
Digital Strategic Orientation	2.094	0.054	0.985	0.888
Empowered Employee Engagement	1.637	0.041	0.990	0.865
Data-Driven Intelligence Culture	2.482	0.062	0.985	0.873

Structural equation modeling (SEM) in AMOS 24.0 tested direct and mediating effects, while PROCESS Macro Model 1 in SPSS 26.0 examined moderation.

RESULTS

Measurement Model Validation

Prior to hypothesis testing, a confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) was conducted to assess the measurement models' validity and reliability. All constructs demonstrated acceptable model fit indices and high internal consistency. The competitive intelligence perception capability (CIPC) construct yielded a comparative fit index (CFI) of 0.968, root mean square error of approximation (RMSEA) of 0.060, and χ^2/df of 2.365, indicating a good fit. Similarly, digital strategic orientation (CFI = 0.985, RMSEA = 0.054), empowered employee engagement (CFI = 0.990, RMSEA = 0.041), and data-driven intelligence culture (CFI = 0.985, RMSEA = 0.062) all met established thresholds for model acceptability (Hair et al., 2019). Cronbach's alpha values for all latent constructs exceeded the recommended threshold of 0.70, confirming strong internal reliability. Furthermore, Harman's single-factor test was employed to assess common method bias. The results showed that a single factor explained only 33.98% of the total variance, well below the 50% critical threshold, suggesting that common method bias was not a significant concern in this study.

Hypothesis Testing

All main hypotheses were supported (Table 5).

TABLE 5. Summary of Hypothesis Testing Results

Hypothesis	Path	β	p-value	Supported
H1	DSO \rightarrow CIPC	0.184	0.002	Yes
H2	DIPI \rightarrow CIPC	0.127	0.020	Yes
H3	EEE \rightarrow CIPC	0.329	<0.001	Yes
H4	DDIC \rightarrow CIPC	0.266	<0.001	Yes
H5	CIPC \rightarrow Performance	0.641	<0.001	Yes
H6a–d	PEU moderates	All $\beta > 0.169$	All $p < 0.001$	Yes
H7a–d	PISA moderates	All $\beta > 0.161$	All $p < 0.001$	Yes

Direct Effects

The structural equation model (SEM) was used to test the direct relationships between the four organizational antecedents and CIPC. As shown in Table 5, all four hypotheses were strongly supported. Empowered employee engagement (EEE) emerged as the most potent predictor of CIPC ($\beta = 0.329$, $p < 0.001$), followed by data-driven intelligence culture (DDIC) ($\beta = 0.266$, $p < 0.001$), digital strategic orientation (DSO) ($\beta = 0.184$, $p = 0.002$), and digital institutional process innovation (DIPI) ($\beta = 0.127$, $p = 0.020$). This finding underscores the pivotal role of human capital and organizational culture over purely structural or strategic factors in cultivating CIPC. The model also confirmed that CIPC is a robust driver of organizational performance ($\beta = 0.641$, $p < 0.001$), supporting H5.

Mediating Effects

To test the mediating role of CIPC (H5a–d), a bootstrapping procedure with 2,000 resamples was performed. The results, presented in Table 6, provide full mediation evidence. The indirect effect of EEE on organizational performance through CIPC was the strongest ($\beta = 0.222$, 95% CI [0.139, 0.310]), followed by DDIC ($\beta = 0.178$, 95% CI [0.104, 0.252]), DSO ($\beta = 0.125$, 95% CI [0.052, 0.203]), and DIPI ($\beta = 0.089$, 95% CI [0.020, 0.161]). In all cases, the confidence intervals did not include zero, confirming significant mediation. This implies that the four organizational management practices do not directly enhance performance; instead, their value is fully realized through their capacity to build a strong CIPC, which in turn drives superior outcomes.

Moderating Effects

The study further examined the contingent roles of perceived environmental uncertainty (PEU) and perceived information source availability (PISA). Using PROCESS Macro Model 1 in SPSS 26.0, the analysis revealed that both moderators significantly strengthened all four main relationships. For instance, the interaction effect between DSO and PEU on CIPC was positive and highly significant ($\beta = 0.212$, $p < 0.001$). Simple slope analysis (Figure 2) demonstrated that the positive relationship between DSO and CIPC was steeper under conditions of high PEU than under low PEU. This pattern was consistent across all antecedents for both moderators (all $p < 0.001$). These findings suggest that the benefits of investing in digital orientation, process innovation, employee empowerment, and an intelligence-driven culture are amplified in turbulent, unpredictable environments and when high-quality data is readily accessible.

Model Fit and Summary

The final integrated SEM demonstrated an excellent overall fit to the data ($\chi^2/df = 1.362$, RMSEA = 0.031, CFI = 0.984), reinforcing the robustness of the theoretical framework. In summary, the empirical analysis provides comprehensive support for the proposed model, highlighting a clear pathway from organizational design to strategic intelligence and, ultimately, to enhanced organizational performance. The findings not only validate the qualitative insights but also offer a quantitatively grounded and nuanced understanding of the mechanisms at play in the big data environment.

Theoretical Implications

This study advances competitive intelligence literature by reconceptualizing CIPC as a dynamic, organizationally embedded capability. Unlike static models of CI, our framework emphasizes *process-efficacy duality*, capturing both the mechanics and outcomes of intelligence work.

We extend organizational adaptation theory by specifying *how* organizations adapt to big data environments—not through ad hoc responses, but through strategic orientation, institutional redesign, human empowerment, and cultural transformation. The finding that EEE is the strongest predictor challenges technology-centric views and reaffirms the role of human agency in data-driven contexts.

Furthermore, by validating PEU and PISA as moderators, we respond to calls for contingency-based theories in strategic management [22]. The results suggest that organizational efforts to build CIPC are most effective under conditions of high uncertainty and high data accessibility—precisely the conditions characterizing the modern business landscape.

Practical Implications

Managers seeking to enhance CIPC should prioritize four interrelated strategies:

1. **Cultivate Digital Strategic Orientation:** Institutionalize digital alertness through scenario planning and competitive simulations. Invest in AI-driven market monitoring tools.
2. **Innovate Digital Processes:** Embed data governance into operational workflows. Establish cross-functional teams to design agile intelligence processes.
3. **Empower Employees:** Implement “train-and-trust” programs that combine digital literacy training with decentralized decision rights.
4. **Foster Data-Driven Culture:** Promote the belief that “data is a strategic asset.” Encourage experimentation with visualization, predictive analytics, and digital war-gaming.

6. Limitations and Future Research

This study has limitations. First, the sample is skewed toward manufacturing firms in China’s Yangtze River Delta. Future research should adopt multi-country, multi-industry designs. Second, the cross-sectional data preclude causal inference. Longitudinal or panel studies could trace the evolution of CIPC over time. Third, the model focuses on organizational factors; future work could integrate technological (e.g., AI maturity) and environmental (e.g., regulatory pressure) variables using the TOE framework [23].

CONCLUSION

In an age where data abundance coexists with strategic uncertainty, competitive intelligence perception capability is not merely advantageous—it is existential. This study demonstrates that CIPC is not an emergent property of technology alone, but the outcome of deliberate organizational design. By anchoring data-driven intelligence in strategy, process, people, and culture, enterprises can transform big data from a challenge into a strategic compass.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

There is no conflict of interest.

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